

15th ISAJ Annual Symposium

**Indian Scientists
Association in Japan**

**Transformative Technologies
for a Sustainable Future**

PROGRAM & ABSTRACTS

**VCC Auditorium, Embassy of India, Tokyo,
Japan**

29th OCTOBER 2024

Indian Scientists Association in Japan

特定非営利活動法人

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<https://isaj.jp>

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Messages

MESSAGE

I am happy to note that the Indian Scientist Association in Japan (ISAJ) is organising its 15th Annual Symposium with the theme, "Transformative Technologies for a Sustainable Future" at Embassy of India in Tokyo.

India-Japan Science and Technology Cooperation was formalised in 1985, and this collaboration has supported a number of collaborative research projects, joint labs and exchange of students, scientists and researchers. The alumni associations of these collaborative efforts have been contributing significantly in pushing forward India-Japan Cooperation in the S&T space. As one of the important associations, ISAJ has already organised 14 such symposiums and has been bringing out newsletters regularly. It provides a platform for scientists from both countries to share their knowledge products in the S&T Domain. These partnerships not only facilitate the exchange of technology and expertise but also foster cultural and intellectual exchanges that enrich both nations.

The theme of the current symposium is apt, as we are moving towards Viksit Bharat by 2047. Transformative technologies are going to play a critical role in achieving this goal. India taking giant leap in S&T is marked by landing on the Moon, COVID vaccines and number of supercomputing facilities such as Param Rudra, Param Shivay, Car-T Cell therapy and many more.

India has undergone transformational changes in the S&T and Education domains, measured by its growth in cementing top positions in the number of scientific publications, patent filing & grants and improvement in the Global Innovation Index ranking. Several mission mode programs, the New Education Policy and the Anusandhan National Research Foundation are posed to play a transformative roles in the nation's progress. Let us leverage these reforms in our S&T Cooperation and academic exchanges for a better and sustainable future by developing & deploying technologies and highly trained human resources at the service of society.

The Embassy of India is pleased to host this day-long deliberations showcasing the research work by Indian and Japanese scientists. I complement the organising committee of 15th ISAJ symposium and convey my best wishes for all such endeavour.

(Sibi George)

Tokyo
October 23, 2024

On behalf of the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ), we extend our warmest greetings to all the distinguished delegates and guests attending the 15th Annual Symposium. This year's theme, "Transformative Technologies for a Sustainable Future," promises to offer an intellectually enriching and thought-provoking experience.

ISAJ is a non-profit organization (NPO) founded in 2008 as a vibrant community platform for Indian scientists working in Japan. In January 2009, Dr. R. Chidambaram, the then Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India, formally inaugurated ISAJ in the esteemed presence of His Excellency Hemant Krishan Singh, the former Ambassador of India. Since its inception, ISAJ has made remarkable strides.

In 2010, ISAJ officially registered as a nonprofit organization (NPO) in Japan, demonstrating its dedication to promoting academic growth and scientific collaboration. Over the years, ISAJ has actively organized seminars, facilitated community discussions, and created networking opportunities for individuals at all levels, from aspiring undergraduate students to experienced academic and industry professionals.

This essential role has brought together countless scientists and researchers, providing young Indian students with invaluable professional training and experience in Japan. ISAJ's efforts have significantly advanced India-Japan cooperation in science and technology, making it a crucial catalyst for mutual progress and scientific exchange.

The Annual Symposium has been a flagship ISAJ calendar event for the past 14 years. Today, we take immense pride in commemorating its 15th anniversary. As customary, this symposium remains dedicated to showcasing the remarkable research endeavors undertaken by Indian researchers and their counterparts in Japan. We have witnessed robust and diverse participation from various multidisciplinary fields each year. The first seven symposia were held in the main auditorium of the Embassy of India in Tokyo. Subsequently, the eighth was held on the Tokyo University campus, the ninth at the AIST Tsukuba campus, and the tenth ventured to the Kansai region, settling at the Osaka University campus. The eleventh symposium was conducted online due to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, defying physical limitations. The 12th Annual Symposium featured a hybrid format, combining on-site and online components, and was hosted by Tokai University in Shimizu, Shizuoka City. The 13th symposium took place at the Embassy Auditorium, while the 14th was held at Hokkaido University. This year, we are returning to the Embassy at the VCC Auditorium. This year

is more special as we are also celebrating Ayurveda Day.

We are committed to maintaining the symposium's interdisciplinary format, creating a platform for participants to exchange ideas and experiences. The numerous scientific presentations over the years clearly demonstrate the diverse and expanding scientific and technological fields in which Indian researchers are actively involved in Japan. It is also encouraging to see a growing trend of Indian researchers rising through the ranks, taking on roles as young researchers and faculty members in Japan, and securing positions at esteemed universities in India.

We warmly welcome our esteemed guests and eagerly anticipate engaging in profound interactions. Notably, the presentations by young researchers have consistently shone as the highlights of our previous symposia, and we have every reason to believe that this year will be no exception. We also await insights from our senior scientists, who will share their extensive experiences working in Japan and valuable contributions to furthering India-Japan science and technology cooperation.

We are sincerely convinced that this occasion is a unique opportunity for all of us to transcend our daily routines and the confines of our specialized research roles. We have complete confidence that coming together on this platform will yield numerous benefits for young Indian students and researchers in various significant ways.

We would like to express our heartfelt gratitude to His Excellency Mr. Sibi George, the Ambassador of India to Japan, as well as all the distinguished dignitaries who have graciously joined us for the 15th Annual Symposium. We sincerely thank all our guests for accepting our invitation and making the journey to be part of this event. We hope that all participants enjoy the symposium and take full advantage of this excellent opportunity to foster connections, build new friendships, and collaborate, thereby strengthening the bonds of science and technology cooperation between India and Japan.

With best regards,

(Sunil Kaul)

Chairman

(Alok Singh)

Vice-Chairman

(Kedarnath Mahapatra)

General Secretary

Welcome Message from the Conveners

We, the conveners, would like to warmly welcome all our esteemed guests and participants to 15th Indian Scientists' Association in Japan (ISAJ) Annual Symposium on “Transformative Technologies for a Sustainable Future”. This event marks the 15th anniversary of ISAJ and coincides with India's Ayurveda Day celebrations. We are grateful to all the participants for sharing our enthusiasm in supporting this symposium by presenting their research findings. We are aware that some of you have traveled long distances to be here today and are immensely grateful for that. We would also like to thank the members of the symposium organizing committee for extending their unstinted support towards the success of this symposium.

We are happy to have received an overwhelming response for in-person presentations. We express our gratitude to the plenary and invited speakers for accepting our invitations readily. We are overwhelmed by the response to our call for abstracts from participants associated with academic and research institutions across Japan. In total, this symposium will be hosting 5 Plenary Talks, 14 Invited Talks, and 32 Poster Presentations by participants from the Kantō (Tōkyō, Tsukuba, Yokosuka, Kawasaki, Isehara), Chūbu (Shizuoka, Iwata, Niigata), Kansai (Kyōto), Kyūshū (Kitakyūshū), Tōhoku (Akita, Sendai), and Hokkaidō (Sapporo) regions of Japan.

This symposium brings together eminent researchers, professors, early-career researchers, and students from diverse fields of science and technology including but not limited to materials science, renewable energy, medicine, seismology, environmental science, quantum photonics, music generation, data science, and food science. The sessions are planned to be multidisciplinary in nature to allow experts and young researchers from diverse backgrounds to share their expertise, thereby providing a unique opportunity to learn outside of their specialized domains and to innovate their ideas and research outcomes for the benefit of science and society. For the encouragement of young researchers, four Best Poster Awards will be presented in the closing ceremony, as in the previous years.

We will continue to seek your assistance in improving this annual symposium in the future and we welcome all suggestions and recommendations for making it even better. It is our sincere wish that this ISAJ Symposium gives you the impetus to continue your research pursuits. We hope you enjoy all the exciting sessions during this one-day event.

We thank you all for your presence, and we welcome you once again to the 15th Annual ISAJ Symposium!

Aaditya Manjanath
Convener

Deeksha Arya
Convener

Sahiba Bano
Convener

15th Annual Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)
Transformative Technologies for a Sustainable Future
29th October, 2024 (Tuesday), Embassy of India, Tokyo

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Plenary Talk Abstracts

PL-1

Development of thermoelectric materials and devices for waste heat power generation and IoT power sources

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Development of thermoelectric (TE) materials is important, for energy saving via waste heat power generation, and IoT power sources [1]. For high TE performance, tradeoffs must be overcome, between Seebeck coefficient S and electrical conductivity σ , and between electrical and thermal conductivity κ [2]. To combat the latter, in addition to nano-microstructuring for selectively scattering phonons to lower κ , we discovered various intrinsic low κ mechanisms: materials informatics approach, particular doping leading to lattice softening, heterogeneous bonding from mixed anions, etc [3]. For the first tradeoff, magnetism can be utilized to enhance S via magnon drag in e.g. Fe₂VAl-based thin films, CuFeS₂, paramagnon drag in CuGaTe₂, Bi₂Te₃, etc., spin fluctuation, spin entropy, etc. [4]. Anderson localization was also utilized to enhance thermoelectrics [5]. Theory and measurements also newly developed [6]. Recently, defect engineering achieved for the first time Mg₃Sb₂ [7] materials to rival long-time champion Bi₂Te₃, via striking Cu doping effect in: interstitial doping lowered the phonon group velocity, while grain boundary doping led to very high mobilities similar to single crystals. An initial realistic 8-pair module exhibited efficiency of 7.3% @320°C, while tuning toward RT yielded cooling of 56.5 K [8]. Further, a single element Mg₃Sb₂ device achieved efficiency 12.6% [9].

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PL-2

Development of Sustainable Urban Digital Twin with Computational Urban Management

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Recently, the term "smart city" has gained widespread popularity as a concept that represents futuristic cities utilizing cutting-edge information technology. Examples of such cities include autonomous driving cities with zero accidents or cashless cities equipped with numerous surveillance cameras. However, it is important to acknowledge that the majority of cities worldwide are not large or extraordinary, and their focus should be on sustainability for the benefit of their citizens. In this regard, fostering collaboration between citizens and local governments, utilizing self-controlled data that is not exclusively governed by a single stakeholder, such as a large corporation, becomes crucial. To address this need, the introduction of the "People Flow Project" and the "Geospatial Information Center" is proposed as research initiatives based on data governance. Furthermore, the "My City X" project is aimed at providing citizens with collaborative urban planning tools, including the "My City Forecast" for predicting city developments, and the "My City Report" for monitoring civil infrastructure. These tools will leverage a city dashboard, various types of open data, and machine learning techniques to facilitate effective urban management.

PL-3

Coastal conservation and sustainable coastal development using artificial seaweed “C-lant”

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Introduction

As global climate change progresses, marine ecosystems are also affected. In recent years, coastal seaweed beds have been decreasing due to land reclamation for coastal development, rising seawater temperatures, and a rapid increase in the population of herbivorous organisms. Seaweed beds function as spawning and nursery grounds for many marine organisms, as well as facilitating material circulation between land and sea. The decrease in this important habitat leads to the deterioration of coastal biodiversity and the decrease of fishery resources. Artificial seaweed beds can be created in various places, even in places where it is extremely difficult for natural algae and seagrass to grow.

Materials and Methods

The artificial seaweed called “C-lant” has a structure that can withstand strong waves. 300 pieces of standard type of C-lant (5cm x 200cm) were attached to sandbags and those were installed on the coast of Shizuoka City, Shizuoka Prefecture on July 19, 2021. The condition of the C-lant in the sea and the gathering and spawning behavior of marine organisms were observed once a month with an underwater camera.

Results and Discussion

On October 1, 2021, a typhoon struck the C-lant test area, but by the end of the observation in February 2022, no damage and loss of the C-lant was observed. In addition, during the seven-month, a total of 38 species was confirmed, and the spawning behavior of the bigfin reef squid was also observed. From these results, it suggests the possibility to establish new spawning and nursery grounds anywhere by using C-lant.

Similar experiments were conducted in the coasts of Eritrea and Cambodia, and the results confirmed that artificial seaweed beds attract fish and crabs in tropical zone. We believe this method is worthy as an emergency measure to protect local ecosystems and fisheries resources, which are important for industries and livelihoods in coastal area. And new spawning and nursery grounds made by C-lant can be a trigger to make new community based fisheries managements and to increase the area capability for sustainable future.

PL-4

**A multiscale simulation without empirical parameter
for designing structural materials**

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In order to realize a carbon-neutral society by 2050, the DX (Digital Transformation) of material development is expected to lead to the short-term development of new structural materials. Generally, structural materials at high temperatures are expected to be used for a long period of time (10 years or so). It is important to improve the service temperature of structural materials, reduce their weight, and extend their service life.

Therefore, it is necessary to create technologies that lead to efficient production of new materials based on theoretical design guidelines. However, most of the material theories are phenomenological theories derived from experimental and observational results. To overcome this problem, our group are developing a multi-scale simulation technique based on reliable first-principles calculations in the nano-scale and obtain results that connect first-principles calculations to the mechanical properties and synthesis technology of materials. I will show some examples of our recent progress such as (1) Electronic structure analysis of light-element-doped anatase TiO₂ coating for visible-light photo-response bone compatible materials, and (2) prediction of microstructures of alloys combining nano-scale first principles calculations and macro-scale phase field simulation method.

PL-5

Data-driven materials research: NIMS initiatives

Masahiko Demura

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We have been collecting materials data for many years and have built a databases suite called MatNavi. AtomWork-Adv, an inorganic materials database, contains more than 360,000 crystal structures, and PoLyInfo, a polymer database, contains more than 29,000 unique polymer structures. These are curated from academic papers. Another database, KINZOKU, is based on datasheets that we ourselves have tested to investigate the reliability of metallic materials for more than 40 years.

The data era is upon us. Data-driven research based on large amounts of data is expected to bring innovation to materials development. MatNavi is a promising data source, and we need to promote its utilization in response to the data age.

It is also important to collect data generated from daily research activities. The data that can be collected from papers is limited to data that is fit for purpose and does not contain so-called negative data. Raw measurement data and details of measurement conditions are also generally difficult to collect from papers. Therefore, we have been working since 2017 on the development and application of fundamental technologies to collect daily research data. After various trials and errors, it became clear that it is effective to implement structuring and registration of data on the spot as they are generated, which led us to develop a data structuring and registration system named RDE for this purpose. Currently, research data are accumulated daily from more than 100 devices of experimental equipment in NIMS.

Based on the above practices at NIMS, the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) has launched the Materials DX Platform Initiatives throughout Japan around 2022. The initiatives consist of three national projects: the Advanced Research Infrastructure for Materials and Nanotechnology (ARIM), which promotes the sharing of facilities and data, the Materials Data Platform, which provides the infrastructure for accumulating and utilizing data, and the Data creation & utilization-type Material R&D project (DxMT), which promotes data-driven materials research. In the presentation, I will outline the activities of data-driven materials research and the infrastructure development in NIMS.

Invited Talk Abstracts

IL-1

CALPHAD-based Thermodynamics for Permanent Magnets

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Nd-based sintered magnets have been used widely in motors and generators. The typical fabrication process of the magnets is presented in Fig. 1 where the heat treatment is one of the key steps in controlling the magnetic properties of the final products. At the sintering, the green compact is densified, and the optimum microstructure is formed at the annealing in which the Nd₂Fe₁₄B (magnetic phase) is separated clearly by the lanthanide-rich grain boundary (GB) phase. To understand the microstructure evolutions during these steps, the phase equilibrium calculations based on computational thermodynamics can provide various insights. Within the framework of CALPHAD (CALculations of PHase Diagrams) methodology [1], thus we constructed a database for the Nd-based sintered magnets, which are partially opened through the NIMS database system [2]. Since the Nd-based sintered magnets consist of various elements,

Fig. 1 Fabrication process of the sintered magnets

accordingly our current database covers the eight major elements (Nd, Fe, B, Cu, Al, Co, Dy, Ga, H) [3]. Moreover, for estimating the effect of oxygen, as the lanthanide elements such as Nd and Dy have high oxygen affinity, we constructed another database for the system with oxygen which covers Nd, Fe, B, Cu, Dy, O [4]. This database considers the ionicity in liquid. In this talk, some results of the thermodynamic calculations on PANDAT [5] and OpenCALPHAD codes [6] will be presented to demonstrate how the phase equilibrium calculations can be applied to the Nd-based sintered magnets.

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IL-2

Caging Bioactive Triarylimidazoles: An Innovative Way of Designing Visible-Light Activatable Drugs

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Small-molecule inhibitors have gained importance as promising therapeutic agents in cancer treatment; however, their efficacy is often compromised by side effects stemming from the inability to confine drug activity to specific regions and the emergence of resistance. To address these challenges, there is a pressing need for innovative strategies that enhance selectivity and localized action of these antitumor agents. Fortunately, photopharmacology has emerged as a potential solution. This innovative field involves the incorporation of photoresponsive components into drug molecules, facilitating dynamic control over their activity.

In this study, we developed a novel caging method targeting the triarylimidazole moiety, a critical structural element in various small-molecule inhibitors targeting kinases in anticancer therapies. We specifically focused on **SB431542**, a triarylimidazole-based small-molecule inhibitor known for its potent and selective inhibition of TGF- β type 1 receptors (TGF- β R1), particularly ALK4, ALK5, and ALK7. We synthesized the photocaged form by modifying the imidazole ring with dimethylamino group, transforming its structure from planar to tetrahedral 2H-imidazole. The cleavage of the C–N bond upon visible light irradiation restored the bioactive **SB431542**, allowing for targeted action. Through wound healing assays with human breast cancer cells, we demonstrated that photocaged **SB431542** selectively inhibited cell migration upon visible light exposure. This caging method provides a versatile strategy for regulating drug activity, thereby minimizing adverse effects and reducing the risk of resistance in cancer therapies.

Reference:

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IL-3

Quantum Photonics on a Tapered Optical Fiber

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We are exploring quantum light-matter interaction on tapered optical fibers with subwavelength diameter waist, referred to as nanofibers, to realize versatile all-fiber platforms for quantum photonics applications. The key feature of the technique is that the guided optical field can be tightly confined in the transverse direction while enabling strong interaction with the surrounding medium in the evanescent region. These features have led to surprising possibilities to manipulate single atoms and fiber-guided single photons.

Fig. 1: (a) Interfacing trapped single atoms with fiber-guided photons to realize a quantum node. (b) Plasmon-enhanced fiber-coupled single photon generation using quantum dot and gold nanorod deposited on nanofiber.

In one direction, we are developing a quantum interface between trapped (laser-cooled) single atoms and fiber guided photons [1]. As shown in Fig. 1(a), single atoms are trapped using optical tweezers and are interfaced with a photonic crystal (PhC) nanofiber cavity. This enables real-time observation of trapped single atoms via fiber-guided modes. In the other direction, we are developing plasmon-enhanced fiber-in-line quantum light sources using a hybrid system of single quantum dots and gold nanorod deposited on a nanofiber (as shown in Fig. 1(b)) [2]. These all-fiber platforms may serve as building blocks for future quantum networks and secure quantum communication protocols.

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WTS: A Pedestrian-Centric Traffic Video Dataset for Fine-grained Spatial-Temporal Understanding

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In this paper, we address the challenge of fine-grained video event understanding in traffic scenarios, vital for autonomous driving and safety. Traditional datasets focus on driver or vehicle behavior, often neglecting pedestrian perspectives. To fill this gap, we introduce the WTS dataset, highlighting detailed behaviors of both vehicles and pedestrians across over 1.2k video events in over hundreds traffic scenarios. WTS integrates diverse perspectives from vehicle ego and fixed overhead cameras in a vehicle-infrastructure cooperative environment, enriched with comprehensive textual descriptions and unique 3D Gaze data for a synchronized 2D/3D view, focusing on pedestrian analysis. We also provide annotations for 5k publicly sourced pedestrian-related traffic videos. Additionally, we introduce LLMScorer, an LLM-based evaluation metric to align inference captions with ground truth. Using WTS, we establish a benchmark for dense video-to-text tasks, exploring state-of-the-art Vision-Language Models with an instance-aware VideoLLM method as a baseline. WTS aims to advance fine-grained video event understanding, enhancing traffic safety and autonomous driving development.

Dataset page: <https://woven-visionai.github.io/wts-dataset-homepage/>.

IL-5

Atomistic Modelling of Materials: Applications to thermoelectrics

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First principles density functional theory (DFT) based simulations not only provide a microscopic understanding of material properties but also gives access to information that are often either inaccessible to experiments or are difficult to measure experimentally. Moreover, using the knowledge gained from these calculations one can rationally design novel materials with improved/new functionalities. In my talk I will briefly discuss the application of DFT based simulations to understand and design thermoelectric (TE) materials that are used in devices to convert waste heat to energy.

Designing efficient thermoelectric materials are challenging because the transport properties that determine the efficiency of a TE material are interdependent and in a reverse way. In our group we focus on understanding the properties of half Heusler alloys for applications as high temperature thermoelectric materials. While these alloys have excellent electrical conductivity and Seebeck coefficient, their performance is poor because of very high thermal conductivity. In this talk I will present our recent work where we have studied complex half Heusler alloys, namely, double Half Heuslers and high entropy Half Heuslers. We have shown that introduction of hierarchial bonding and mass disorders can be effective strategies to reduce the lattice thermal conductivity and thereby improve the thermoelectric performance of the material.

IL-6

Carbonized polymer microspheres: fluorescent micro-emitters for encrypted photonic barcodes and anti-counterfeit applications

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Developing advanced security features is crucial for combating counterfeiting and ensuring the authenticity of high-value products. This research investigates carbon-based solid-state microphotonic emitters, specifically carbonized polymer microspheres (CPMs).^{1, 2} These emitters exhibit exceptional solid-state fluorescence (SSF) across the visible to near-infrared (NIR) spectrum, leveraging the unique properties of carbon dots (CDs) alongside the photonic characteristics imparted by their spherical shape. When excited, photons experience multiple reflections via total internal reflection (TIR) at the surface of the microspheres, effectively functioning as a cavity. By exploiting their excitation-dependent photoluminescence, CPMs can achieve amplified spontaneous emission through whispering gallery mode (WGM) resonance within the visible to NIR range. Unlike conventional semiconductor quantum dots or dye-doped microresonators, these microstructures enable adaptive resonant emission without requiring structural or chemical modifications. This distinctive capability facilitates the creation of encrypted photonic barcodes for advanced anti-counterfeit measures. By merging nanophotonics with materials chemistry, this interdisciplinary approach presents a robust solution for SSF materials, offering wide-ranging applications in security and authenticity verification. The development of CPMs with inherent photonic functionality and excitation-dependent emission properties paves the way for next-generation encrypted barcodes and anti-counterfeit technologies, ensuring product integrity and authenticity in various high-value sectors.³

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IL-7

Study on the characteristics of black pine defoliation and sustainable utilization of defoliated pine needles

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The global environment is experiencing a marked warming trend, which needs to be mitigated by introducing innovative methods and technologies. This study focused on the deciduous pine leaves growing in various regions of the world, especially the Japanese black pines (*Pinus thunbergii*). A seasonal growth cycle is observed in which the black pine trees drop their leaves as winter approaches. The amount of defoliation is so large that the ground becomes like a carpet.

It is well known that the growth of pine trees, including the black pines, is augmented by a healthy symbiotic relationship between the defoliated pine leaves and mycorrhizal fungi in the soil. However, mycorrhizal fungi are inhibited by high nutrient levels in the soil, suppressing the growth of pine trees. Finding ways to sustainably utilize the defoliated pine needles, which would prevent soil enrichment, could be one step toward mitigating global warming and creating new energy resources.

Against the above background, we developed a technology to sustainably utilize the fallen pine needles by pelletizing them. As a part of the technology development, the combustion temperature of the pine needle pellets was kept at the same level as that of commonly used cedar pellets, and the feasibility study was conducted using the pellets in stoves and other devices, confirming the effectiveness of the pine needle pellets. We also examined methods for evaluating the abundance of pine needles by placing litterfall traps under two black spruce trees to study monthly litterfall for approximately three years, from October 2018 to September 2021. The results showed an average of 18.3 g/m² of black spruce litterfall per month. The long period of the study allowed us to successfully capture characteristics related to seasonality and the impact of events such as typhoons on defoliation. By extrapolating the results of the two black spruce trees obtained in this study, we could quantify the distribution of defoliation in black spruce forests across Japan using GIS.

IL-8

Green Synthesis of a Flexible Metal-Organic Framework [Cu(BF₄)₂(4,4'-bipyridine)₂] (ELM-11) for Selective CO₂ Adsorption

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Developing cost-effective and eco-friendly adsorbents is crucial for reaching the 2050 carbon neutrality goal. Elastic Layer-structured Metal-organic framework-11 (ELM-11), a flexible MOF with the formula [Cu(BF₄)₂(bpy)₂] (bpy = 4,4'-bipyridine), exhibits energy-efficient carbon capture potential with high working capacity and intrinsic thermal management (**Fig 1a**).¹ However, the conventional synthesis of its precursor, pre-ELM-11 [Cu(BF₄)₂(bpy)(H₂O)]₂·bpy, involves organic solvents in addition to H₂O. In this research, we achieved pre-ELM-11 synthesis using only H₂O at room temperature and studied the CO₂ adsorption, kinetics, and CO₂/N₂ gas separation behaviors of its dehydrated form ELM-11.

The pre-ELM-11 was synthesized in 83-84% yield at 25 °C using only H₂O as both reaction and washing solvent. The CO₂ uptake of H₂O-synthesized ELM-11 was slightly higher than that of MeOH/H₂O-synthesized ELM-11 (**Fig. 1b**). It also exhibited a slightly lower gate-opening pressure (**Fig. 1b**). The isosteric heat of adsorption (Q_{st}) for both samples was 24 kJ/mol, indicating easy regeneration. (**Fig. 1c**). Our synthetic method is economical and environmentally friendly for scalable, real-world CO₂ sequestration applications.

Fig. 1 (a) Crystal structures of hydrated form, pre-ELM-11 and its dehydrated form, ELM-11. (b) CO₂ sorption isotherms measured at 273 K for ELM-11 samples synthesized from H₂O and MeOH/H₂O. (c) Isosteric heat of adsorption (Q_{st}) of H₂O-synthesized and MeOH/H₂O-synthesized ELM-11 samples calculated from CO₂ sorption isotherms obtained at 273 K, 283 K, and 298 K.

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Harnessing Sustainable Formulation Technologies: Evaluating the Viscoelastic and Sensorial Attributes of a Natural Oil Emollient Cream

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The emergence of transformative technologies in cosmetic formulations is paving the way for sustainable and consumer-compliant products. This study investigates an emollient cream formulated with neem oil (*Azadirachta indica* A. juss) and the biodegradable emulsifier Montanov 202, which aligns with ecological principles while ensuring effective skin care. The viscoelastic properties of the cream were evaluated through oscillatory measurements, revealing a favorable balance between storage and loss moduli, indicative of its structural integrity and user-friendly application. Optical polarized microscopy confirmed the presence of lamellar liquid crystalline and gel crystalline phases, enhancing hydration potential and consumer appeal. Sensory evaluations conducted with female volunteers indicated that the neem emollient cream exhibited superior consistency and reduced oiliness compared to a commercially available neem-based cream. Principal component analysis identified key sensory attributes that contribute to user satisfaction, highlighting the importance of molecular structure and formulation in achieving desirable sensorial experiences. By harnessing sustainable ingredients and innovative formulation technologies, this study demonstrates a pathway towards creating effective and environmentally friendly cosmetic products that meet modern consumer expectations.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica* A. juss, Montanov 202, Emollient cream, Viscoelasticity, Sensorial analyses, Consumer Compliancy

Implementation of three-dimensional effects in tomographic techniques using elastic waves based on ray-tracing for plate-like structures

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Tomographic technique based ray-tracing has been used for the investigation of underground, and further, the soundness evaluation of structures in recent. For applying this technique for the plate-like structures, the three-dimensional effects should be appropriately considered if it is not negligible. Nevertheless the straight way is three-dimensional modeling of a target structure to consider the three-dimensional effects, the structure is modeled in two-dimensional manner since the three-dimensional modeling results in a costly calculation. The authors proposed a pseudo three-dimensional technique for adequately considering the three-dimensional effects with limited computational resources. However, in the technique, the shape of the ray-path is determined without considering the inhomogeneity of the elastic wave velocity in thickness direction. Thus, in this study, a technique that considers the inhomogeneity of the elastic wave velocity in thickness direction is proposed.

The proposed technique is verified by performing a series of numerical investigations. In the numerical investigations, a model in which the elastic wave velocity changes along the ray-path is generated, and the ray-paths that are computed by the proposed technique and a method that is premised the three-dimensional modeling respectively are compared, and it is shown that the proposed technique demonstrates.

IL-11

Lithium Diffusion in Perovskite-Type Solid Electrolytes Revealed by PFG-NMR and TOF-SIMS

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Solid-state batteries are expected to serve as next-generation energy storage systems due to their safety, reliability, and high energy densities. The oxide-based solid electrolytes have achieved ionic conductivities of the order of 10^{-3} S cm⁻¹, internal resistance of solid-state battery is still high due to resistance at grain boundaries. Typically, the analysis of ion dynamics has been performed by ion conductivity measurements. Recently, we have developed a method to determine bulk diffusion coefficients using pulsed field gradient nuclear magnetic resonance (PFG-NMR). In addition, grain boundary diffusion has been determined by a new method using secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) [1, 2].

These methods were applied to polycrystalline solid electrolytes, La_{0.57}Li_{0.29}TiO₃ (LLTO). The Li diffusion coefficient of LLTO has been evaluated over a wide range of time scales and temperatures using various experimental techniques (Fig. 1). The grain boundary diffusion is visualized by using SIMS analysis. The relationship between the crystal structure, nanodomains, and grain boundaries of LLTO and the diffusion of lithium ions was experimentally clarified. The conductivity diffusion coefficients and bulk NMR diffusion coefficients were in good agreement. These methods elucidate the bottleneck of ion transfer and contribute to improving the solid-state batteries.

Fig. 1. Li diffusion coefficients of LLTO measured by conductivity, PFG-NMR, and TOF-SIMS.

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IL-12

Damage Progression of CFRP by Means of Acoustic Emission Analysis

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In recent years, several applications of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) in civil engineering structures have been reported. However, the evolution of defects in FRP is still not well known. In addition, evaluation and inspection methods for FRP defects in actual structures are highly required. In this study, a CFRP sampled from existing structure was evaluated for failure evolution during cyclic tensile testing using acoustic emission analysis and digital image correlation (DIC).

The results suggest that the evaluation of AE parameters and the Acoustic Emission Analysis as well as the digital image correlation method, are applicable to the future inspection of FRP structures. In particular, the AE energy and peak frequency during the tensile fracture process of FRP increased with increasing surface strain during the tensile test, suggesting that the evaluation of AE parameters can appropriately detect the tensile fracture process of FRP. The results also suggest that acoustic emission analysis may be applicable to the detection of FRP fracture sites. In particular, the results considering anisotropic velocity distribution agreed well with those of surface strain behavior.

Exploring Food Nutrients and Function with the aid of Mass Spectrometry Technologies

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Lipids are the major components of human blood and are widely distributed across numerous tissues. They are either biosynthesized in mammalian cells or consumed as nutrients from food sources. At present, more than 48,500 lipid molecules are identified from eight major categories including curated and computationally generated. Many studies have proposed that each structurally different lipid molecule has an independent biological function, and there are potential links between the lipid functions and biological phenotypes. However, the comprehensive characterization of food lipidome is still sparse. Our research aims to apply advanced targeted and untargeted liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry techniques to profile lipids in various functional foods to evaluate their nutritional significance and to uncover novel lipids with potential biological benefits. Further, an imbalance in lipid metabolism is commonly observed in various disease pathologies including cancer and obesity. Hence, monitoring the altered lipid levels would be an ideal path for early diagnosis and finding possible therapeutic targets. In this presentation, I will introduce our recent findings on monitoring sphingomyelin synthase (SMS) an enzyme associated with fatty liver disease, and the potential of seaweed hijiki extracts on SMS. The potential of lipidomics to address various challenges in food and health sciences will be discussed.

IL-14

Near-neutral pH sensing by azoheteroarene dyes

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pH indicators are widely used in various disciplines, including material, environmental, biological, and clinical sciences. [1] Broadly, pH indicators are based either on fluorometry or colorimetry, which involves detecting changes in fluorescence or color from the analyte. One major advantage of colorimetry over fluorometry is the ease of detection by the naked eye without any instruments, making it a cost-effective method. Colorimetric pH indicators that can show distinct color changes in a near-neutral pH range are particularly advantageous for detecting pH variations in biological systems. For instance, tissue and cell culture is a routine experiment in many biology laboratories. When tissues or cells are incubated for several days, the waste products from dying cells can cause changes in the pH of the culture medium, which can be detected by monitoring the color change of the indicator.

We have recently discovered distinct photophysical characteristics and molecular geometries of azoheteroarenes. [2, 3] This study reports a new series of azo dyes consisting of heteroaryl motifs that can detect near-neutral pH variations. [4] We found that the azoheteroarene dye can precisely monitor pH even in complex environments such as cell culture medium, allowing us to detect pH changes in the culture medium containing growing cancer cells. Based on the distinct color changes observed in our study, we hope that optimized azoheteroarene dyes can even distinguish cancerous tissue (pH 6.4–7.0) from normal tissue (7.2–7.5).

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Poster Presentation Abstracts

P-1

Highthroughput sputtering synthesis of TbCu₇-type SmFe-based rare-earth lean sustainable permanent magnets

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In sustainable, clean energy technologies like hybrid and electric vehicles, as well as wind turbines, permanent magnets are essential components in motors and generators. (Nd, Dy)-Fe-B magnets are commonly used in these applications because of their high maximum energy product. However, growing demand and the supply risk associated with Nd and Dy have intensified the search for alternative permanent magnets. Sm-Fe-based permanent magnetic compounds have emerged as a potential next generation permanent magnets due to the combination of low supply risk, cost-effectiveness, and sustainability [1,2]. In this work, TbCu₇-type SmFe_x ($x=6.4$ to 12.7) and SmFe_xN ($x=6.8$ to 12.8) composition spread thin films were fabricated using a combinatorial sputtering system to study the effect of composition on the phase formation and extrinsic magnetic properties. A high-throughput phase and composition analysis was carried out using x-ray diffraction and x-ray fluorescence measurements respectively, at different Fe:Sm ratio positions on the thin film. The Fe:Sm ratio significantly affects the formation of main TbCu₇-type phase and the secondary ferromagnetic α -Fe phase. The optimal Fe:Sm ratio, which exhibits the highest fraction of the TbCu₇-type phase free from α -Fe, was identified as SmFe_{9.8} and SmFe_{9.5}N. The coercive field (μ_0H_c) was estimated using a position-dependent polar-magneto-optical Kerr effect hysteresis loops and was found to range from 1.1 T (for SmFe_{6.8}N) to 0.06 T (SmFe_{12.8}N). Overall, this study demonstrates the effect of composition variation on the phase and extrinsic magnetic properties of this compound, facilitating the selection of desired compositions with targeted magnetic properties.

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P-2

An assessment of the impacts of energy transition in Niigata City and Hachinohe City, Japan on atmospheric particles and human health

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This study assesses the impacts of energy transition on atmospheric particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) concentrations and human health in Niigata City and Hachinohe City, Japan. We analysed net-zero carbon emission policies specific to Niigata and Hachinohe, focusing on energy consumption and emissions reduction strategies. Using the GAINS model, we projected changes in energy consumption from 2010 to 2050, estimating corresponding PM_{2.5} concentration reductions. These projections allowed us to estimate premature mortality in 2030 and 2050 under the current energy transition policies. We collected PM_{2.5} concentration data from 2010 to 2020 and calculated premature mortality rates across different age groups in both cities. The annual ambient concentrations of PM_{2.5} shows significant declining trend in both Niigata and Hachinohe cities. The local government policy result in the reduction of fossil energy consumption and corresponding PM_{2.5} emission. Due to the population aging in the small cities, the premature mortality will increase in the 2030 and 2050. The results highlight the health co-benefits of climate change policies driven by energy consumption shifts and also significant negative impact of population aging. This integrated analysis underscores the broader public health advantages of Japan's net-zero carbon emission policies, particularly in smaller urban areas.

Significant Reduction of Thermal Conductivity and Enhancing Thermoelectric Performance in CrSb₂ via Fe-Bi Co-Alloying

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The efficiency of thermoelectric (TE) technology relies on the performance of TE materials[1-2]. Substitution with heavy elements is an effective strategy in TE for enhancing phonon scattering without affecting electrical transport properties[3]. However, selecting suitable dopants to achieve a high thermoelectric Figure-of-merit (ZT) poses a significant challenge. Thus, in this study, the efficacy of combined (Fe and Bi) co-substitution in CrSb₂ is investigated as a promising strategy to enhance ZT by lowering thermal conductivity. A series of co-doped Cr_{1-x}Fe_xBi_ySb_{2-y} (x = 0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1 and y = 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.25) samples were synthesized via furnace reaction followed by spark plasma sintering technique. Phase analysis and temperature dependence electrical and thermal transport properties were systematically studied on synthesized samples. Furthermore, to analyze the impact of disorder induced by Bi/Fe substitution, electronic structure calculation was performed using the projector augmented-wave method. Notably, Cr_{0.75}Fe_{0.25}Bi_{0.15}Sb_{1.85} exhibited a low thermal conductivity of approximately 2.5 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ at 300 K which reduced to half compared to the thermal conductivity of pristine CrSb₂ (~5 W/m K). This is attributed to the introduction of significant mass fluctuations and point defects along with the presence of Bi at grain boundaries by co-substitution, resulting in the strain field fluctuation. Consequently, a remarkable 90% enhancement in ZT (~0.021) at 350 K was achieved for Cr_{0.75}Fe_{0.25}Bi_{0.15}Sb_{1.85} compared to pristine CrSb₂ (ZT~0.012). This study can provide valuable insights into the rational design of effective dopants in other TE materials also.

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Task Planning Using Large Language Models and Semantic Maps For Open Vocabulary Assistance in Service Robots

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Open Vocabulary refers to a system's ability to understand, interpret, and respond to a wide range of natural language inputs without being constrained to a set of predefined set of commands. Open vocabulary task execution is a crucial capability in autonomous robotics, particularly for indoor service robots operating in dynamic, human-centric environments.

We consider the task of searching for dynamic objects in an indoor environment called Object Search. While the state-of-the-art approaches focus on most effective ways to search for a closed set of objects, we propose a framework that is capable of generalizing to unknown, unseen, and ultimately an open-set of objects. Our framework consists of a method to leverage priors of a fixed-set of objects to generate task-driven priors for an open-set of objects. We utilize Large Language Models (LLMs) and semantic maps to facilitate this prior generation. Finally, we validate our framework through extensive real-world experiments and provide comparisons with competitive methods, demonstrating its effectiveness in generalizing to an open-set of objects. The results also demonstrate our framework's superiority in reducing search time, distance, and number of visited landmarks, outperforming related methods.

Surface morphology- engineered thermal and UV blocking hybrid thin film with ITO nanoparticles and Carbon dots

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Global rise in temperature has led to high power consumption in buildings. Achieving a temperature drop of only 1°C indoors could reduce energy costs by 1-3% for an 8-hour usage. To aim at such reduced costs thermal heat shielding materials are crucial. Designing window coatings using near infra-red (NIR) and harmful ultra-violet (UV) radiation blocking materials render cooler and safer interiors as seen in Fig. 1(a). Oxide semiconductor materials like titanium dioxide, vanadium dioxide, indium tin oxide and cesium doped tungsten oxide serve as wavelength selective absorbers due to their high NIR tunability and high transparency in the visible region, but they exhibit reduced efficiency in UV-A (315-400 nm) absorption. Thus, in this presentation we propose a hybrid thin film, of indium tin oxide nanoparticles (ITO NPs) and eco-friendly carbon dots (CDs), hereby called ITO+CDs as a simultaneous NIR and UV blocking window coating material that provides high transparency in the visible region. CDs provide very high UV-A absorption while promoting aggregation of ITO NPs to form a porous, thin film. Enhanced absorption in the NIR was assigned to light scattering/trapping from such pores in the film. Tuning thickness of the ITO+CDs film increased porosity leading to improved NIR absorption, seen in Fig. 1(b). Finally, ITO+CDs film showed solar blocking capacity of 90% in the UV-A and 74% in the NIR regions with high visible transmittance. For the same amount of ITO nanoparticles, ITO+CDs film showed greater performance reducing the use of ITO to achieve a certain efficiency. We demonstrated thermal shielding effect through an architectural model with simulated solar illumination (A.M. 1.5G) on a window glass with only ITO NPs vs ITO+CDs film coating. Figure 1(c) shows temperature inside the house as a function of the exposure time for different thicknesses of the ITO+CDs coating and ITO NPs with same solar exposure. The difference in room temperature (thermocouple placed close to the floor) was 8°C between ITO NPs and ITO+CDs. Oxide semiconductor nanoparticles and environment friendly, sustainable carbon dots are potential materials as efficient NIR and UV blockers for window and skylight coating applications.

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Fig. 1 (a) Schematic showing selective light absorbing ITO+CDs thin film as window/skylight coating (b) Transmittance spectra of ITO+CDs with varying thicknesses (c) Temperature vs time of ITO+CDs and ITO NPs

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Unraveling The Rafting Mechanism In Nickel-base Single Crystalline Alloys Through Phase-Field Simulations

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Nickel-base single crystalline superalloys are used in the most critical parts of aero engines (High-pressure turbine fan blades). They are subjected to uniaxial stresses due to the fan's rotation during high-temperature operation. Understanding their microstructure is crucial for enhancing their performance in such extreme conditions. This study utilizes phase-field simulations to investigate the directional coarsening behavior (rafting) of γ' precipitates under applied stress and elevated temperatures. The phase-field method is a powerful tool for modeling the complex interplay between elastic anisotropy, lattice misfit, and applied stress that drives the rafting process. We have simulated rafted microstructures in model single crystalline Ni-base alloys, accounting for the multiple variants of the ordered γ' phase. Our results on rafting directions show consistency with earlier theoretical analyses based on elastic energy.

To further explore the rafting mechanism, we conducted single precipitate simulations under varying conditions, including different applied stresses, lattice misfits, and inhomogeneities between the γ and γ' phases. Our findings indicate that stress distribution in the vertical and horizontal channels influences the chemical potential of solute atoms, causing them to diffuse from the precipitate interface in one channel and redistribute in the other, ultimately leading to a rafted microstructure. Moreover, the stress distribution is sensitive to elastic properties such as the extent of inhomogeneity, signs of misfit, and degree of anisotropy.

P-7

Selective Organ Targeting of Nanomedicines via In Situ Stealth Coating of Liver Scavenger Endothelial Cells

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Selective ORgan Targeting (SORTing) of nanomedicines offers tremendous potential for improving the diagnosis and treatment of various diseases. However, reticuloendothelial tissues, particularly liver scavenger endothelial cells, capture most of the injected nanomedicine dose, significantly reducing delivery efficiency to target disease sites and raising toxicity concerns. We addressed this issue by *in situ* poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) coating to the liver endothelium using one- or two-armed PEG-conjugated oligo(L-peptide) (PEG-OligoPeptide). Both one- and two-arm-PEG-OligoPeptides selectively attached the liver endothelium, leaving the endothelium of other tissues uncoated and thus accessible to nanomedicines. The two-arm-PEG-OligoPeptide was gradually removed from the liver endothelium and progressively accumulated in bile (transient coating) (**Figure 1**). In contrast, one-arm-PEG-OligoPeptide remained on the liver endothelium, resulting in prolonged disruption of normal physiological functions of the liver. Ultimately, the transient and selective stealth coating of the liver endothelium by two-arm-PEG-OligoPeptide effectively prevented the liver elimination of nanomedicines, thereby boosting their delivery efficiency to the target tissues such as tumor, spleen, and heart. Indeed, our coating agent, two-arm-PEG-Oligo(L-Ornithine), is currently being used in human clinical trials to deliver therapeutic small interfering RNA to patients with recurrent breast cancer. Phase I clinical results confirm its safety and replicate the pharmacokinetics in humans, as observed in mice.

Figure 1. Transient stealth coating of the liver scavenger endothelium with two-arm-PEG-OligoPeptide to prevent the capture of nanomedicines by the liver.

P-8

Materials Degradation and Their Protection Against Ammonia Environment at Elevated Temperatures for Exclusive Ammonia Fueled Gas Turbines

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Decarbonization of the society to combat global warming is of major interest worldwide in the current scenario. Reduction of greenhouse gases and carbon emission through the utilization of green fuel for power generation have significant positive impacts on the global climate. Ammonia, a carbon-free energy carrier, have attracted substantial attention recently as a direct fuel in gas turbines. However, being a highly corrosive and toxic chemical compound, the effective utilization of ammonia poses several challenges in terms of the degradation of materials used in the turbine components. Therefore, understanding of the materials degradation and development of environmental protection against ammonia corrosion is indispensable.

Inconel 600, a high-strength metal used in different components of gas turbines was exposed to ammonia gas flow at elevated temperatures to understand its corrosion behaviour. The effect of gradual ammonia decomposition in the direction of ammonia flow on the extent of surface degradation was investigated. Significant damage of the material in terms of cracking and spallation was identified even after a short duration exposure test in ammonia. The damage mechanisms were also studied utilizing different characterization tools like, XRD, TEM, and Optical Emission Spectroscopy (OES). Longer duration tests of Inconel 600 and Hastelloy X also revealed significant surface damage at relatively lower temperatures upto 600 °C.

The durability of thermally sprayed CoNiCrAlY coating and Ytria-stabilized Zirconia (YSZ) Thermal Barrier Coatings (TBC) under such extreme corrosive environment containing ammonia was also studied. Therefore, the present work revealed that the metallic materials are susceptible to severe degradation and hence, require environmental protection against ammonia.

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Controlled Synthesis of Jarosite and Schwertmannite and their Comparative Removal Analysis for Toxic Oxyanions

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Biogenic iron hydroxysulfates (BIHS) have increasingly recognized as potential adsorbents for heavy metals with better biocompatibility in wastewater treatment. BIHS are formed through the oxidation of ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}) by iron oxidizing bacteria such as *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans*. Schwertmannite ($\text{Fe}_8\text{O}_8(\text{OH})_5(\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$), a BIHS, has been extensively studied for its effectiveness in removing various oxyanions, including selenate (Se(VI)). However, jarosite ($\text{KFe}_3(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_6$) an inherently more stable BIHS compared to schwertmannite, lacks prior research on its Se(VI) removal ability. Therefore, the present research aimed to investigate the controlled precipitation of different iron hydroxysulfates by utilizing *A. ferrooxidans*. The resulting precipitates were characterized as jarosite and schwertmannite using X-ray diffraction. Morphology and elemental composition were identified using scanning electron microscopy and ICP-MS. Further, Se(VI) adsorption by these precipitates in a liquid medium was studied. The results showed that the size of jarosite particles, which was modulated by adjusting the initial pH of the medium, played a pivotal role in Se(VI) adsorption. Notably, jarosite with smaller particle size (1-2 μm) exhibited a comparable Se(VI) adsorption capacity to schwertmannite, an effective Se(VI) adsorbent. Conclusively, this study highlights to a new prospective application of jarosite in Se(VI) removal from wastewater through its controlled synthesis techniques.

Keywords: Jarosite, Schwertmannite, Adsorption, Selenate

Advancing Sustainable Geotechnical Design: Insights into Frictional Behavior of Non-Dilative Interfaces

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As the demand for sustainable engineering practices grows, numerical simulations such as the Discrete Element Method (DEM), Finite Element Method (FEM), and coupled FEM-DEM are vital tools in geotechnical engineering. These methods address complex interactions at non-dilative interfaces, which are crucial for optimizing resource use and minimizing environmental impacts. However, their accuracy depends on two factors: the contact models used and the selection of input parameters. Non-dilative interfaces transfer loads through friction without dilation, governed by sliding and plowing, often deviating from traditional soil mechanics models like Amonton's law. More precise force prediction models, grounded in particle-level experiments, are essential for capturing this behavior across scales. This study introduces a custom-designed shear testing apparatus developed to simulate conditions relevant to sustainable geotechnical applications. A series of experiments was conducted to investigate how angular particles' meso- and micro-level features influence the frictional behavior and coefficient of non-dilative interfaces under varying normal loads. Geomembrane, widely recognized for its sustainable benefits in geotechnical projects, was used as the continuum material. Particle surface roughness was measured using an optical profilometer to establish a correlation between roughness and frictional mechanisms. Results revealed that an increase in average surface roughness by approximately 44 percent led to a 37 percent rise in the friction coefficient. Moreover, the friction mechanism shifted from sliding to plowing with increasing normal loads. These findings offer crucial insights into the complex interactions at non-dilative interfaces, which can be applied to enhance data-driven force prediction models. This advancement contributes to more sustainable engineering practices by improving both design precision and material efficiency, aiding in the development of environmentally responsible geotechnical solutions.

P-12

Shell model study of beta-decay in neutron-rich $N = 126, 125$ nuclei along the r-process path

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The rapid neutron capture process (r-process) is the most important mechanism for the synthesis of about half of the elements heavier than iron. It occurs in an environment with relatively high temperatures and high neutron densities. The abundances of the elements created by the r-process strongly depend on several nuclear inputs like masses, neutron capture rates, beta-decay rates, and beta-delayed neutron emission probabilities at the waiting point nuclei. Among them, the beta-decay process plays a crucial role in the r-process. We have investigated various nuclear beta-decay properties of $N = 126, 125$ isotones with proton numbers $Z = 52-79$ within the framework of the nuclear shell model. This comprehensive analysis considered both Gamow-Teller (GT) and first-forbidden (FF) transitions to evaluate beta-decay rates. We have found that including FF transitions in addition to GT transitions is essential, as they significantly impact the total beta-decay half-lives near $Z = 82$. Additionally, we systematically analyzed the GT strength distributions as a function of proton number. We have observed that the GT strengths at low excitation energies are rather strong on the proton deficient side due to the increasing number of proton holes in the proton $0h_{11/2}$ orbit, which accelerates GT decay. This investigation aims to provide detailed information on beta-decay properties around $A \approx 195$ to understand the distribution of the third r-process abundance peak.

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P-12

Low Cycle Fatigue of Inconel 718 and Crystal Plasticity Modelling

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Nickel-based superalloys, such as Inconel 718 (IN718), are widely used in aerospace applications, particularly for manufacturing jet engine components like turbine blades and compressor discs due to their excellent high-temperature mechanical properties. Fatigue, driven by cyclic loading during startup and shutdown operations, is a primary failure mechanism in these components [1][2]. The fatigue life of such materials is heavily influenced by microstructural features, including grain size distribution and the presence of second-phase particles, which can act as sites for fatigue crack initiation[3][4]. However, the variability in microstructure, caused by different manufacturing processes and heat treatments, leads to scatter in fatigue life, making empirical fatigue models like Coffin-Manson and Basquin inadequate for capturing the microstructure's influence on fatigue behavior. The research involves strain-controlled, completely reversed low cycle fatigue (LCF) testing. Generally, under strain controlled cyclic loading, IN718 exhibits an initial hardening followed by softening till failure [5]. This softening behavior is often attributed to the precipitates, specifically the ordered gamma double prime γ'' , present in the alloy. The coherent γ'' precipitates are continuously sheared by the forward and backward movement of dislocations under cyclic load resulting in loss of strengthening ability of the precipitates, eventually leading to softening [6][7]. This study aims to develop a crystal plasticity-based framework for fatigue life prediction in IN718 incorporating softening behavior observed in In718. Microstructural characterization will also be performed using techniques such as SEM and TEM. The gathered microstructural data and fatigue stress-strain behavior will be integrated into the crystal plasticity framework, enabling accurate modeling of fatigue life based on microstructural variability. This work seeks to advance the understanding of microstructural effects on fatigue properties and improve fatigue life prediction for aerospace components.

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P-13

Does Seaweeds can protect us from fatty liver disease associated with dysregulated lipid metabolism?

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Over the past 40 years, obesity rates have surged worldwide, becoming a major public health concern. This rise is closely linked to metabolic syndromes such as dyslipidemia, fatty liver disease, cardiovascular diseases, and type 2 diabetes mellitus. A key factor behind these disorders is an imbalance in lipid metabolism, often driven by altered activity of lipid-metabolizing enzymes like sphingomyelin synthase (SMS). Disruptions in SMS function affect sphingolipid homeostasis, contributing to the progression of obesity-related diseases. Despite seaweeds having potential health benefits their role in obesity control associated with lipid metabolism is poorly investigated. In this study, we screened organic extracts of various seaweeds to discover potential SMS inhibitors using a liquid-chromatography/mass spectrometry coupled *in vitro* assay method developed earlier in the laboratory. They further, carried out molecular docking studies with optimized structures of SMSs.

Our findings revealed that the hexane extract of hijiki seaweed exhibited strong inhibitory activity against both SMS1 and SMS2. Further analysis led to identifying and characterizing the active compound as a long-chain fatty acid (LCFA), which is responsible for the SMS inhibition. LCFA (FA 22:1) demonstrated IC₅₀ values of 4.5 μM for SMS1 and 6 μM for SMS2. To evaluate the potential of fatty acids as SMS inhibitors we have screened 42 fatty acid compounds and found that pentadecanoic acid (FA 15:0) is very potent in inhibiting SMSs (IC₅₀ values of 13 μM for SMS1 and 45 μM for SMS2). To support these results *in-silico* molecular docking studies were conducted, which confirmed strong binding affinities of FA 22:1 and FA 15:0 with SMS proteins. These findings highlight the potential of these compounds as promising therapeutic agents targeting lipid metabolism, offering a novel approach to addressing metabolic syndromes, such as obesity.

P-14

Preventing Sn²⁺ Oxidation in FASnI₃ Perovskite Precursors and Improving Solar Cell Stability Using Reductive Additives

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Tin-based halide perovskite solar cells (Sn-PSCs) are gaining increasing interest as an effective replacement for lead-based PSCs (Pb-PSCs). A solution process spin-coating approach is used for fabricating Sn-perovskite films. Due to the low chemical stability of tin iodide (ii)-dimethyl sulfoxide (SnI₂-DMSO) and the oxidation of Sn²⁺ to Sn⁴⁺, the power conversion efficiency (PCE) fluctuates for different batches of precursor solution. This study examined the source of Sn²⁺ oxidation prior to film formation, revealing that the ionization of SnI₂ induces the oxidation of free Sn²⁺ and I⁻ ions [1]. To address this challenge, the study introduced 4-fluorophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (4F-PHCl) as a reductive additive to the FASnI₃ perovskite precursor solution [2]. The hydrazine functional group (-NH-NH₂) in 4F-PHCl converted harmful Sn⁴⁺ and I₂ defects back into Sn²⁺ and I⁻, while retaining the perovskite solution's original properties. Furthermore, the addition of 4F-PHCl slowed the crystallization process, improving the crystallinity of the FASnI₃ perovskite films and maintaining the stoichiometric ratio of Sn²⁺/I⁻. This approach resulted in a PCE of 10.86%. The hydrophobic fluorinated benzene ring in 4F-PHCl enhanced the moisture stability of the perovskite films, allowing unencapsulated PSCs to retain over 92% of their initial PCE in an N₂-filled glovebox for 130 days. Additionally, 4F-PHCl-modified encapsulated PSCs exhibited superior operational stability, retaining 95% of their initial PCE after 420 hours under maximum power point tracking at 1 sun continuous illumination.

Fig. 1: J-V curves of pristine and 10% 4F-PHCl modified PSCs.

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P-15

A Study on Differences in Carotenoid Content in the Heirloom Sweet Potato Variety 'Ninjin-imo' Group

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In Japan, the heirloom sweet potato variety 'Ninjin-imo' was often used as a dried sweet potato because the root mass was colored like a carrot, producing a unique texture and flavor. However, the differences between breeding lines and varieties called 'Ninjin-imo' have not been sufficiently investigated. Therefore, in this study, we tested seven breeding lines and varieties of 'Ninjin-imo' and clarified the difference in carotenoid content.

In 2023, 13 breeding lines and varieties in total, including seven of 'Ninjin-imo' and six varieties other than 'Ninjin-imo,' were investigated, and comparative cultivation was conducted at the field of the Faculty of Agriculture, Shizuoka University. Cuttings were carried out from seedlings in early June, and a yield survey was conducted on October 27. Carotenoids were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) at the Faculty of Agriculture, Shizuoka University.

The difference in total carotenoid content between 'Ninjin-imo' breeding lines and varieties was observed. The highest total carotenoid content was found in the breeding variety 'Hamakomachi,' which was about 2.9 times that of the heirloom sweet potato 'Ninjin-imo' (Kakegawa) and 159.3 times that of 'Beniharuka.' The highest yield was for 'Hamakomachi' (2062.5 g/strain), and for 'Ninjin-imo' (Kakegawa), it was 773.4 g/strain. These results suggest that 'Hamakomachi' is a variety with excellent carotenoid content and yield. The 'Ninjin-imo' group had a significantly higher total carotenoid content than the 'Beniharuka.' Since the total carotenoid content of the breeding variety 'Hamakomachi' was about 2.9 times that of the heirloom 'Ninjin-imo' (Kakegawa).

Considering the results of this study, strategies such as improving yield (virus-free), and developing the quality of products such as the heirloom sweet potato variety, 'Ninjin-imo' should be used in the region. Furthermore, branding the products with high unit prices might help achieve such a goal. We hope that the functionality of β -carotene should be used to promote the heirloom sweet potato variety 'Ninjin-imo.'

P-16

Quantized Conductance Atomic Switch Network based on Ag-Ag₂S Core-Shell Nanoparticles

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The atomic switch network (ASN) has emerged as a potential candidate for mimicking synaptic plasticity, a key function of biological synapses, and holds significant promise for applications in neuromorphic computing¹. Through quantized conductance, ASNs exhibit behavior analogous to synaptic connections, enabling the modulation of conductance states similar to biological synapses adjust their strength. In this work, we have demonstrated the quantized conductance behavior of an ASN using Ag-Ag₂S core-shell nanoparticles. Figure 1a shows an analogy of signal transmission in biological synapses and atomic switch networks. The network shows synaptic plasticity such as short-term and long-term memory and quantized conductance states with integer multiples of a $2e^2/h$ (G_0) of a single atomic point contact. Figure 1b shows the conductance (in a unit of G_0) versus voltage (V) plot obtained with an Ag-Ag₂S nanoparticles network at room temperature. The initial jump from 0 to 1 G_0 signifies the formation of a single atomic point contact between the two electrodes. As the applied bias increases, the filament thickens, creating additional conductive channels that result in higher multiples of G_0 . Our results indicate the network's potential to exhibit quantized conductance states, which are the basis of multilevel memory.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic representation of the signal transmission in a biological synapse, elucidating the analogy with Ag/Ag₂S core shell nanoparticles network. (b) Conductance (in the unit of G_0) versus voltage plot obtained with nanoparticles network.

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Rational design of cyclopentadiene-based super- and hyperacids based on aromaticity

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The design and synthesis of neutral organic superacids are of recent interest due to their vast applications in chemistry and material sciences like olefinic polymerization, isolation of highly reactive short-lived cations, etc. Cyclopentadiene behaves as a mild organic acid, producing a stable conjugate base by gaining aromaticity and conjugation after deprotonation. To stabilize conjugate bases of organic acids to show superacidities and hyperacidities, we have considered aromatic phenyl substituents with cyclopentadiene (mono, di, and tri phenyl substituted cyclopentadiene and their cyano derivatives). The MP2, DFT (B3LYP, M06-2X), and CBS-QB3 methods have been used to calculate the gas phase proton affinities of parent cyclopentadiene and have chosen the DFT methods for substituted cyclopentadiene as DFT methods produce the experimental proton affinities of cyclopentadiene of 253.66 kcal/mol (Expt. 253.6 ± 1.3 kcal/mol). The stable tri-substituted cyclopentadiene derivative shows the gas phase enthalpies of deprotonation (ΔH_{acid}) of 245 kcal/mol and 239 kcal/mol at DFT B3LYP and M06-2X respectively, with values in the range of hyperacidity. Some of the protonic tautomers of cyclopentadiene derivatives show hyperacidity, which shows the proton affinity values of 205 kcal/mol to 240 kcal/mol. Tri-phenyl substituted cyclopentadiene behaves as a moderate acid and becomes a superacid after replacing the phenyl with nitrobenzene, a stronger acid than H₂SO₄ ($\Delta H_{\text{acid}} = 298$ kcal/mol). The nuclear independent chemical shift (NICS) shows the extent of conjugation in the derivatives of cyclopentadienyl anions after deprotonation, which affects the stabilities of conjugate bases, i.e., the acidities of molecules.

P-18

The Effect of Anti-CLIC1 Antibodies in Reducing Breast Cancer Cell Invasion via Inhibition of Chloride Ion Efflux

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The metastasis of breast cancer remains particularly threatening, as cancer cells preferentially spread to blood, brain, and bone tissue, making late-stage breast cancer difficult to treat. Chloride Intracellular Channel Protein 1 (CLIC1) is a chloride ion channel overexpressed in various cancers and may be a potential therapeutic target. Previously, we found that CLIC1 is activated by the stretching of the cell membrane due to external mechanical force. The efflux of chloride ions via CLIC1 during a process known as regulatory volume decrease (RVD), leads to cell volume reduction and shrinkage of cancer cells therefore CLIC1 blockers are expected to inhibit cancer cell invasion. In this study, we used monoclonal anti-CLIC1 antibodies that bind to the extracellular region of CLIC1 protein and evaluated their effect in inhibiting Cl⁻ efflux and preventing cancer cell invasion. A 27 amino acids peptide sequence, which is the CLIC1 extracellular region, was used for immunization to obtain rabbit anti-CLIC1 monoclonal antibody clones. Mechanical force to induce Cl⁻ efflux was applied to the cells using an Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) and flat tip cantilever and the fluorescence was analyzed to evaluate the Cl⁻ efflux inhibition by antibodies. We confirmed that some were able to prevent chloride ion efflux and there was a correlation between antibodies being able to prevent chloride ion efflux and being able to reduce cancer cell migration. Immunostaining of the cells using the antibodies revealed differences in antibody localization sites which may be responsible for the variations in chloride ion efflux inhibition and cancer cell invasion. From this we identified antibody clones suitable for further development of breast cancer therapeutics.

Fig. 1 Mechanism of antibodies inhibiting Cl⁻ efflux

Primordial group transfer potential: Exploring the chemistry of thioacetate

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“Where Do We Come From?” is a fundamental question to humans. Origin of Life research is the field on how initial life was born and evolved on the early Earth. In this study, we focus on group transfer potential in prebiotic metabolism. While thioesters have been proposed to have been relevant molecules with high group transfer potential, thioacetate is simpler since it requires an only carbonyl group and sulfide, rather than a carbonyl and a thiol. The hydrolysis energy of the C-S bond in thioacetate and thioesters is almost equal to the phosphate bond of ATP. Thus, this molecule is thought to be the precursors of ATP in protometabolism, and thioacetate could have served as a central intermediate energy conversions.¹ So, it can be said thioacetate is quite important and relevant for prebiotic metabolism and the origin of life, however, the chemistry of thioacetate is largely un-explored. Here I'll present a project about thiolysis reaction concerning the study of thioacetate. Thiolysis means the degradation of thioester into thioacid in the presence of sulfide. We observed thiolysis with the goal of understanding early energy exchange between thioesters and thioacids.

As the problem of regarding thioacetate as the center of primordial metabolism network, it is said that the speed of hydrolysis of thioacetate into acetate is usually so rapid that thioacetate can't accumulate abiotically enough². However, it seems specific conditions can suppress this speed. We found out the speeds of hydrolysis and thiolysis are dependent on pH, and so the state of thioacetate is. Dominant chemical species are different at each pH, which suggests that the role of thioacetate could be different according to the pH of surrounding environments. We can draw different models how thioacetate could contribute to prebiotic metabolic networks for each pH, each possible sights for the origin of life.

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Keywords: origin of life, prebiotic metabolism

Real-Time Viability Detection of Drug Resistant Bacteria Using Growth Curve, PMA Treatment and RT-PCR

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The increasing prevalence of drug-resistant bacteria presents a significant health threat, necessitating rapid and accurate identification techniques. To address this challenge, we developed a protocol that simultaneously identifies the bacterial composition of clinical samples and their drug-resistance profiles. In this method, we assessed the antibiotic susceptibility of bacterial strains by monitoring growth curves and treating them with various antibiotics at different concentrations. Propidium monoazide (PMA) was used to inhibit DNA amplification from dead bacteria, followed by RT-PCR to confirm the presence of live target microorganisms in both untreated and antibiotic-treated samples. Traditional culture-based techniques can take several days to identify bacteria and determine antibiotic susceptibility. In contrast, our method significantly reduces turnaround time, facilitating timely clinical decision-making. When tested with resistant and sensitive bacteria, the growth of sensitive strains significantly decreased compared to resistant strains in the presence of certain antibiotics. Following this, PMA effectively differentiated dead bacteria from live ones, as confirmed by RT-PCR. This scalable protocol provides a valuable tool for rapidly profiling drug-resistant bacteria.

Synthesis and thermoelectric properties of high-entropy-type CoSb₃ skutterudite

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CoSb₃-based skutterudites are among the most promising candidates for thermoelectric devices at intermediate temperatures due to their high carrier mobility, electrical conductivity, and relatively large Seebeck coefficient. Comparatively, having the high room temperature thermal conductivity ($10^{-15}\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) of binary skutterudites results in a low ZT value which restricts its use in practical applications. The decrement in the lattice thermal conductivity (k_L) is an effective approach to improve the performance of thermoelectric materials for practical applications. In this regard, the high-entropy-alloy (HEA) is one of the best strategies to enhance the required phonons scattering by lattice disorder because of its high configurational entropy of mixing (ΔS_{mix}). HEAs are developed with five or more principal elements in equimolar or near equimolar ratio, producing a random solid solution with a simple crystal structure like BCC or FCC. The resulting new crystal structure shows significant disturbances, strain, and severe lattice distortion which induces the necessary phonons scattering into the lattice. Thus, it is expected that the HEAs possess low k_L resulting from severe lattice distortion. To avail this strategy, we have synthesized HE-type CoSb₃ skutterudite compounds and found a large reduction in k_L value in HE-type compounds. Also, we have successfully synthesized the Indium filled HE-type skutterudites to take the rattling motion of indium into account for further decrease in k_L value. We will discuss the preparation and effect of HEA on the thermoelectric properties of CoSb₃ skutterudite in detail. Additionally, the effect of indium filling on the thermoelectric properties of the HE-type CoSb₃ compound will be discussed.

Keywords: thermoelectric, high-entropy-alloy, skutterudite, phonon scattering, lattice thermal conductivity

Development of High Performance BiFeO₃-based Multiferroic Thin Films for Magnetic Device Applications

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Energy consumption in magnetic devices can be reduced by utilizing electric field control of magnetization. BiFeO₃-based multiferroic thin films, with room temperature magnetoelectric coupling, offer great potential for this approach. Achieving favorable magnetic properties in BiFeO₃ is crucial for magnetic device applications. We successfully fabricated single-phase (Bi,L)(Fe,Co)O₃ (L = La, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Er) thin films, all exhibiting ferromagnetism and ferroelectricity. Notably, (Bi,Eu)(Fe,Co)O₃ thin film demonstrated a high saturation magnetization of around 130 emu/cm³ and a low coercivity of about 0.8 kOe, ideal for nano-sensor devices.

For nano-device applications, BiFeO₃-based thin films must undergo microfabrication without damage. To assess etching resistance, (Bi,Eu)(Fe,Co)O₃ thin film dots (10 μm) were fabricated using reactive ion etching (RIE). Magnetic properties were examined under etching conditions with rates exceeding 1.0 nm/min.

Figure: Comparison of coercivity change between etched area and unetched area of (Bi,Eu)(Fe,Co)O₃ thin films in RIE Cond 2 and 5.

Under condition 5 (no oxygen), coercivity increased, surface roughness decreased, and magnetic domains expanded due to oxygen desorption and crystal structure changes, while minimal changes were observed under condition 2, as shown in the figure.

P-23

Full Waveform Inversion Technique (Adjoint Tomography) for Seismic Imaging of Nankai Region, Japan By Utilizing Advanced Python-Based Seismic Analysis Tools.

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In the pursuit of envisaging sustainable and resilient societies, understanding the intricate dynamics of Earth's crust is crucial, particularly in seismically active and densely populated regions of the world. Although earthquake prediction is still a challenge for scientists, our goal is to illuminate the subsurface structure responsible for the heterogeneities like low velocity fluid saturated zones, fractured rock layers, volcanic channels, sedimentary basins, accretionary wedges or high velocity sea mounts, subducted slabs, oceanic rocks. The Nankai-Kyushu subduction zone in Japan is characterized by complex seismotectonic interactions presenting a prime region for advanced technique like seismic imaging. In this study, we employ an advanced earthquake-based, full-waveform inversion technique (Adjoint tomography) known as adjoint tomography to develop a high-resolution shear wave velocity model. This is done by developing and utilized advanced Python-based seismic tools for mathematical modelling, data processing and visualization, and interpreting efficiency using heavy seismic data signals. It has been previously applied to regional, continental, and global scales, with a proven track record of high probing applicability in subduction regions elsewhere in the world (e.g., Chow et al., 2022). We leverage ~400 moderate-sized earthquake events ($4.5 < M_w < 6$) recorded by ~150 permanent land stations and ~20 temporary Ocean Bottom Seismometers (OBS) deployed in the Southern Kyushu coast. We setup 3D wavefield simulations and assess the accuracy of existing velocity models before conducting inversion process to improvise to accuracy by quantifying the misfits between data and synthetics (travel-time residuals, amplitude ratio and peak cross-correlation values). Adjoint tomography can be extended to the collision zones of the Himalayas and the Indian Ocean to interpret lateral heterogeneities, velocity anomalies, and their relationship to genesis of earthquakes. This study will highlight the computational technique adopted to arrive at such velocity models which can provide critical insights for seismic hazard mitigation and sustainable development in these densely populated and seismically active regions.

Lithium Diffusion Dynamics in Lithium Lanthanum Niobate: A TOF-SIMS and Isotope Exchange Approach

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In this study, we explore the lithium-ion diffusion properties of lithium lanthanum niobate (LLNbO), a perovskite-type oxide renowned for its high ionic conductivity. The material's unique crystal structure facilitates efficient lithium-ion transport, positioning it as a promising candidate for solid-state ionic applications. We employ a stepwise isotope exchange technique using a ^6Li -enriched solution to determine the diffusion coefficient of LLNbO single crystals. Post isotope exchange, the lithium distribution and relative isotopic ratios (^6Li and ^7Li) within the crystals are analyzed via time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS). Additionally, we perform TOF-SIMS experiments at various temperatures to evaluate how the diffusion coefficient changes with temperature. From these observations, we derive the activation energy for lithium-ion diffusion in LLNbO, offering valuable insights into its transport mechanisms. The findings could contribute to advancing next-generation energy storage systems, where improving ionic conductivity is key to enhancing battery performance, safety, and longevity.

P-25

Towards a Sustainable AI-Driven Music Preservation Framework

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This poster aims to survey the recent developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven music culture preservation, reflecting on the case studies as well as the ethical challenges in this field. Several case studies, including research on preserving Shanxi Opera [1], imply how AI enhances accessibility and cultural engagement, allowing modern audiences to interact and revive traditional cultures. Apart from interaction, machine learning can be applied to preserve the artefacts of music culture, such as vocal song synthesis that preserves a singing tradition [2]. These studies contribute to a growing sentiment of AI transforming sustainability efforts in music culture. However, it is important to reflect on the social and ethical challenges such applications may pose. Several researchers argue that indiscriminate use of AI in music preservation frameworks may suffer from issues surrounding trust, communication and potential for harm. For example, using AI to preserve vocal traditions may result in bias due to the algorithm's capabilities. Several calls have been made to reflect the necessity to restructure frameworks that apply AI techniques in music preservation. We summarise these and discuss potential future steps.

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**Critical behavior and magnetocaloric effect
in La_{0.67}Ba_{0.33-x}Sr_xMnO₃ (x=0.1, 0.2 and 0.25)**

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We have systematically investigated the critical behavior around paramagnetic-ferromagnetic (PM-FM) phase transition temperature, T_C , and attempted to determine the Curie temperatures and critical exponents β , γ and δ of perovskite manganites La_{0.67}Ba_{0.33-x}Sr_xMnO₃ (x=0.1, 0.2 and 0.25). The T_C determined from $M(T)$ is observed to increase from 336.7 to 368.4 K, with Sr doping at Ba. The critical exponents β , γ and δ are determined from the magnetization, $M(T,H)$, using Modified Arrott Plots for theoretically predicted models and critical $M(H)$ isotherms at $T = T_C$. From the critical exponents we have inferred that La_{0.67}Ba_{0.33-x}Sr_xMnO₃ behave as a three-dimensional (3D) isotropic nearest neighbor Heisenberg ferromagnet in the critical region. We have further verified that the behavior of 3D isotropic nearest neighbor Heisenberg is in agreement with the values of exponent 'n' determined based on the relation between field dependent change in magnetic entropy at the Curie temperature, $T = T_C$. Sr doping at Ba site in La_{0.67}Ba_{0.33-x}Sr_xMnO₃ does not lead to any crossover in the type of magnetic interactions present in the materials, indicating a stable behavior of 3D isotropic nearest neighbor Heisenberg ferromagnet in the critical region. The differences in the values of parameters may be attributed to the complex nature of interactions present in these materials. This material's stability and magnetic properties make it promising for magnetic refrigeration applications, contributing to sustainable development.

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Organosulfur Compounds: Linking Atmospheric Chemistry to the Origins of Life in Earth's Primordial Oceans

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This project investigates the role of sulfur compounds in prebiotic chemistry and their interactions in deep-sea environments, especially regarding the formation of essential biomolecules for the origin of life. It stemmed from pioneering experiments that studied the impact of trace H₂S levels on organic haze development in planetary atmospheres such as Titan and early Earth. By introducing small amounts of H₂S (0.5 to 5 ppm) into a mixture of Methane and Nitrogen and applying UV light, the density of organic aerosol particles was increased. Additionally, this process integrated sulfur into organic molecules, leading to the creation of organosulfur compounds including methyl sulfonic acid and acetyl sulfate. (Reed et al., 2020)

Based on these findings, we hypothesize that the organosulfur compounds such as acetyl sulfate from atmospheric organic haze may fall with rain and interact with phosphates and amino acids in primordial oceans, contributing to synthesizing essential biomolecules. To test this hypothesis, one of the organosulfur compounds, acetyl sulfate, was synthesized by reacting acetic anhydride and sulfuric acid in chloroform. The reaction with potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄) at pH 4-5 produced a solid white precipitate of K₂SO₄ and acetyl phosphate. Moreover, pyrophosphate was also detected. Pyrophosphate is an energy carrier in biochemistry and is involved in biosynthetic pathways. Its formation indicates that K₂SO₄ may act as a catalyst, facilitating reactions on the precipitate's surface potentially increasing acetyl phosphate and pyrophosphate production.

Our research examines a fresh viewpoint, proposing that acetyl sulfate may serve as a vital connection between atmospheric chemistry and the emergence of life in deep-sea environments. We investigate how organosulfur compounds in planetary haze could have journeyed great distances to arrive in Earth's primordial oceans, possibly contributing significantly to the creation of life's foundational elements.

Isolation of Novel Cardenolide Glycosides from *Xysmalobium undulatum* and Their Role in Reducing A β 42 Levels with Insights from South African Medicinal Plants in Alzheimer's Research

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a severe neurodegenerative disorder primarily caused by β -amyloid (A β) peptide accumulation, especially A β 42, known for its harmful aggregation. Addressing this is crucial for developing therapies that may slow or reverse AD progression. My research focuses on the therapeutic potential of South African traditional medicinal plants to find bioactive compounds that lower A β 42 levels.

In 2019, we studied various South African medicinal plants historically used for ailments, specifically their A β 42 modulation ability. By applying ethnopharmacological knowledge, we analyzed plant extracts and identified promising candidates. This foundation led to isolating a novel cardenolide glycoside from *Xysmalobium undulatum* in 2021, which effectively reduced A β 42 levels in vitro, paving the way for plant-based AD therapeutics.

These findings demonstrate traditional medicinal plants' potential as new drug sources for neurodegenerative diseases. Our work merges ethnobotanical insights with modern techniques and bridges ancient knowledge and contemporary science. I look forward to sharing our journey from selecting plant materials to biochemical assays and discussing the importance of natural product research for Alzheimer's treatment. This research provides hope for innovative AD therapies and emphasizes preserving Indigenous medicinal practices.

Laser Beam Induced Current Mapping Characterisation of III-V Semiconductor Solar Cells

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The luminescent Coupling (LC) effect results in the generation of extra photocurrent in lower bandgap (LBG) subcells of the multi-junction solar cell (MJSC) due to the radiative recombination in higher bandgap (HBG) sub-cells. We have studied and compared the characterization for the commercially available lattice-matched InGaP/ GaAs/Ge (LM-3J) and InGaP/GaAs/InGaAs (IMM-3J) solar cells through Laser Beam Induced Current (LBIC) mapping method. This helps in optimizing the design of high-efficiency MJSCs.

In this paper, LM-3J and IMM-3J solar cell samples were characterized at room temperature using the LBIC mapping approach in which a specific subcell is made current limited using a combination of single-wavelength LEDs among 430, 780, 970 and 1550 nm. The 3JSC samples were tested in the short circuit conditions. And the subcell being evaluated is current limited by illuminating appropriate LEDs on nonlimiting subcells, and no illumination on the limiting subcell. To evaluate the in-plane current generation in the subcells, the subcell is excited with a pulsed laser among the wavelengths 450, 785, and 1064 nm, and the wavelength is selected so that it is within the absorption range of the cell. Similarly, to evaluate the spatial LC current collection in the LBG subcell, the wavelength of the pulsed laser selected was within the absorption range of the top HBG subcell [1].

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Thermal Activation in Yielding of Single-Crystalline Tungsten

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Tungsten being a BCC metal is known to exhibit a brittle to ductile transition. Below the transition temperature, tungsten shows brittle fracture because ductility enabling mechanisms like kink-pair-formation of screw dislocations are mostly suppressed. Particularly in safety-critical applications tungsten shall yield instead of fracture. By pushing the yield stress to lower values, we can extend the ductile regime of tungsten and thus lower the temperature for transition. To design tungsten-based materials that can undergo plastic deformation in an extended temperature range, we need to gain a deep understanding of driving mechanisms of ductility. Classical impact tests show the macroscopic material behavior but do not allow insights into the governing mechanisms. Therefore an approach capable of investigating on the nanoscale is required.

In present work we elucidate yielding in defect-free sample volumes of tungsten via nanoindentation. This technique is capable of observing material plasticity³ at tiny length scales (nanometer range). Over a thermal range hardness and pop-in behavior are analyzed. While hardness expectedly decreases with temperature, the critical load where pop-in occurs seems unaffected or even increasing. This suggests a fundamentally different activation mechanism for hardness and pop-in. In our understanding, pop-in is governed by dislocation nucleation whereas dislocation mobility is the main mechanism determining hardness. For pop-in to occur, a high local stress close to or at the theoretical stress limit is required. Therefore pop-in might be predominantly stress-dominated and the thermal activation might not be discernible within the tested temperature range. Analysis of critical stresses and activation parameters is performed to elaborate on the atomic mechanisms.

The results provide a starting point that is essential for tailoring plasticity in future material development.

Analysis of macroalgae cultivation impact in shallow coastal areas

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Seagrass restoration and macroalgae cultivation in coastal areas, as part of the global Blue Carbon (BC) initiatives, are attracting attention and gaining popularity worldwide. The restoration of macroalgae in coastal areas not only aids in carbon sequestration and reducing total greenhouse gasses emissions but also plays a crucial role in ecosystem functioning at remediated coastal areas. In Japan, macroalgae cultivation is not only an economic practice deeply rooted in history but also a reflection of Japanese dietary habits.

In this work, we applied a high-resolution numerical model that considers the benthic ecosystems in shallow coastal areas in Kanazawa Bay, south of Yokohama City, to study the effect that macroalgae cultivation has on the concentration of dissolved organic matter (DOM), particulate organic matter (POM), and dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN). Three study cases: a) actual conditions that include wild and cultivated macroalgae, b) exclusively macroalgae cultivation, and 3) exclusively wild macroalgae, were simulated. The variables of interest were followed for 12 months at three observation points with different types of macroalgae ecosystems and the results were seasonally analyzed. Our findings showed seasonal variations, particularly during the growth period, depending on the types of macroalgae present in the area, which directly impacts the ecosystems in the study area.

The obtained results reinforce the importance and the necessity of good assessment tools for the design and promotion of BC initiatives for the national and prefectural governments, to avoid affecting the ecological balance in coastal regions while maintaining and encouraging environmental solutions on a global scale.

Silicon metasurfaces with strong light confinement and their sensing applications

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Strong confinement and localization of light in nanofabricated structures are of great importance for a wide range of applications [1], including high-efficiency lasers, sensors, bioimaging, nonlinear enhancement, non-Hermitian optics, and topological photonics. The energy dissipation of confined light is quantified by the quality (Q) factor, where both material choice and structural design play a significant role in maximizing the experimental Q factors. Dielectric metasurfaces operating at quasi-bound states in the continuum (qBICs) [2] can achieve exceptionally high radiative quality (Q) factors by introducing small asymmetries into their unit cells [3]. However, fabrication imperfections often impose significant limitations on the experimentally observed Q factors. In this study, we experimentally demonstrate BIC metasurfaces with a record-high Q factor exceeding 10^5 under normal excitation of light in the telecom wavelength range, achieved through the use of shallow-etched paired silicon rods. Our results show that such ultrahigh- Q factors can be attained by leveraging both the high radiative Q factors of higher-order qBIC modes and the reduced scattering losses in shallow-etched designs. Additionally, we observe stable sub-picometer-level wavelength fluctuations in water, with a limit of detection of 10^{-5} for environmental refractive index changes. This approach can be extended to BIC metasurfaces with many other configurations and operating wavelengths for ultrahigh- Q applications in both fundamental physics and advanced devices.

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